

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

Title: SOP for tryptophan metabolite analysis of serum via LC-QQQ

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Author: Kateřina Coufalíková

Summary

The tryptophan metabolites (anthranilate, indole-3-acetamide, indole-3-acetate, indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic acid, indole-3-propionic acid, *L*-kynurenine, *L*-tryptophan, methyl indole-3-acetate, *N*-acetyl tryptophan, tryptamine) perform important signalling and immunomodulatory functions, especially interaction of the innate immune system of the host with PXR or AHR xenobiotic receptors. This protocol describe preparation of serum and quantitative/semiquantitative determination using LC-QQQ.

Preparation

Safety information

- Serum samples are classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.
- Isopropanol: flammable liquids, eye irritation, specific target organ toxicity following single exposure

Equipment

- 100 μ L multichannel pipettes & 1 mL pipettes
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates

Consumables & glassware

- 4 mL screw cap glass vial and cap
- 1000 μ L 96-well plates with silicone sealing

- 250 μ L & 1 mL tips

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

- Serum samples stored in -80 °C freezer and thawed at room temperature

Labelled standard mix:

[¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate acid (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful, irritating

[²H₅] L-kynurenine (99 % isotope enrichment)

[¹³C₁₁][¹⁵N₂] L-tryptophan (99 % isotope enrichment)

[²H₅] [¹⁵N] indole-3-acetamide (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful

[¹³C₆] anthranilate (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful

Indolmix (native standard mix) each = 250 nM in 25 % (v/v) isopropanol

methyl indole-3-acetate – corrosive, irritant

tryptamine - irritant

indol-3-acetic acid – harmful, irritating

L-kynurenine

L-tryptophan

indol-3-acetamide - harmful

anthranilate - harmful

N-acetyl-tryptophan – harmful, irritating

indol-3-aldehyde - irritating

indol-3-lactic acid – irritating

indole-3-propionic acid - irritating

Reagents for mobile phase preparation

- Acetonitrile, LC-MS grade
- Formic acid (FA), LC-MS grade
- MilliQ water

Procedure

Standard preparation

1. Prepare 3 mL aliquots isotopically labelled mix of 1000 nM [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate acid, 40 nM indole-3-acetamide [²H₅] [¹⁵N], 1000 nM [²D₄] L-kynurenine, 1000 nM [¹³C₁₁] [¹⁵N₂] L-tryptophan and 130 nM [¹³C₆] anthranilate in 5 % (v/v) isopropanol
2. Pipette directly or dry the internal reference standard mix down in Centrifugal evaporator at laboratory temperature, store in -80 °C and reconstitute in the solvent before analysis.

Sample preparation

1. NOTE: Store serum samples at -80 °C
2. Take out serum samples from freezer and leave at room temperature to thaw
3. Pipette 50 µL of serum sample and mix with 100 µL water; sonicate (5 min)
4. Extract samples with 350 µL 80% (v/v) isopropanol; vortex (200 RPM at room temperature) for 20 min; centrifuge for 10 min at 4000 RPM (use centrifuge for 96-well plates)
5. Afterwards remove 350 µL of the supernatant
6. To the remaining 50 µL of the sample add 450 µL 80 % (v/v) isopropanol; sonicate (5 min); vortex (200 RPM at room temperature) for 20 min; centrifuge for 10 min at 4000 RPM (use centrifuge for 96-well plates)
7. Afterwards remove 350 µL of the supernatant
8. The extract from two extraction step mix together and dry in Centrifugal evaporator
3. For indol-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic acid, indole-3-propionic, methyl indole-3-acetate, N-acetyl tryptophan and tryptamine determination: Redissolve dry samples in 25 µL isotopically labelled mix containing: 1000 nM [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate acid, 40 nM indole-3-acetamide [²H₅] [¹⁵N], 1000 nM [²D₄] L-kynurenine, 1000 nM [¹³C₁₁] [¹⁵N₂] L-tryptophan and 130 nM [¹³C₆] anthranilate in 5 % (v/v) isopropanol.
9. For anthranilate, indole-3-acetate, L-kynurenine, L-tryptophan determination: Dilute the extracts 50 times.

NOTE: For LC-QQQ analysis in linear range and subsequent quantification dilution is necessary due to relatively high concentration of these metabolites in serum

Mobile phase preparation

- Mobile phase A: 0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water (solution can be kept for 7 days at 4 °C temperature)
- Mobile phase B: 0.1% FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile

NOTE: use at least 5% milliQ water in acetonitrile (prevent LC clogging)

LC-QQQ analysis

4. Clean the source and nebulizer before measurement
5. Check solvent for needle rinsing
6. Check solvent for seals rinsing
7. Prepare mobile phase
8. Input sequence
9. Start LC-QQQ analysis run
10. Check initial blanks, standard mix = Indolmix, Labelled standard mix and QC

NOTE: If problems, stop run, cap samples and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.

NOTE: Measure with every sample set:

- Instrument blank (Mobile phase A)
- Procedural blank (same preparation as samples; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC (pool of samples extract; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC dilution series in 3 replicates (same sample preparation as QC with 2x, 4x, 8x dilution & spiked with Labelled standard mix)
- Indolmix
- Labelled standard mix in 5% (v/v) isopropanol
- Calibration curve in matrix: prepare pool of DBS extract → spike Labelled standard mix (use 6 different concentration) → measure 6 calibration points with 3 replicates (6 replicates for LOD, LOQ determination)
- QC_dilution series in 3 replicates (dilute QC: 2x, 4x, 8x & spike with same concentration of Labelled standard mix)

LC-QQQ sequence setup

1. Clean_blank
2. Clean_blank
3. Instrument blank
4. Indolmix
5. Indolmix
6. Indolmix
7. Labelled standard mix
8. QC_dilution series
9. Procedural blank
10. QC sample
11. Samples 1-3
12. Instrument blank
13. Sample 4-6
14. Instrument blank
15. Sample 7-9

NOTE: measure Instrument blank after every 3 samples

NOTE: measure Indolmix with every 30 samples

NOTE: measure Labelled standard mix minimum 3 times (at the beginning of the batch, in the middle of the batch and the end of the batch)

16. Calibration
17. End with Indolmix, Instrument blank and 2 x Clean blank

Table 1. SRM assay library for positive ion detection mode

COMPOUND	PRECURSOR	PRODUCT	RT [MIN]
L-KYNURENINE*	209.09	192.00	1.6
L-KYNURENINE	209.09	94.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE*	215.13	198.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE	215.13	96.10	1.6
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	144.1	1.9
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	117	1.9
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	115	1.9
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	91	1.9
L-TRYPTOPHAN *	205.10	188.00	2.9
L-TRYPTOPHAN	205.10	91.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN*	218.10	200.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN	218.10	98.10	2.9
ANTHRANILIC ACID	138.06	120.00	7.2
ANTHRANILIC ACID*	138.06	65.00	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID	144.08	126.10	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID*	144.08	70.20	7.2
INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE*	175.09	130.07	7.3
INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE	175.09	103.00	7.3
[² H ₅] [¹⁵ N] INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE*	181.12	134.10	7.3
[² H ₅] [¹⁵ N] INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE	181.12	106.00	7.3
N-ACETYLTRYPHOPHAN*	247.11	188.10	7.8
N-ACETYLTRYPHOPHAN	247.11	130.00	7.8
N-ACETYLTRYPHOPHAN	247.11	118.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	188.00	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	130.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTID ACID*	206.06	117.90	7.8

INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE*	146.06	118.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	117.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	91.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	65.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	39.20	8.0
INDOLE-3-ACETATE*	176.07	130.07	8.2
[¹³ C ₆] INDOLE-3-ACETATE*	182.10	136.10	8.2
METLYLINDOL-3-ACETATE	190.09	130.07	9.3
INDOLE-3-PROPIONIC ACID	190.09	171.86	8.7
INDOLE-3-PROPIONIC ACID	190.09	130.07	8.7
INDOLE-3-PROPIONIC ACID	190.09	102.97	8.7
INDOLE-3-PROPIONIC ACID	190.09	55.06	8.7

* TRANSITION USED FOR QUANTIFICATION

SRM metabolite quantitative/semi-quantitative evaluation

1. For concentration determination of indole-3-acetic acid, *L*-kynurenine, *L*-tryptophan, anthranilate and indole-3-acetamide use internal standardization with isotopically labelled standards [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate, [²D₄] *L*-kynurenine, [¹³C₁₁] [¹⁵N₂] *L*-tryptophan, [¹³C₆] anthranilate and [²H₅] [¹⁵N] indole-3-acetamide.

The calculation is based on the concentration of isotopically labelled standard added to DBS sample, measured response (integrated peak area) of isotopically labelled standard, and response (integrated peak area) of metabolite Equation (1).

$$c_{\text{met}} = \left(\frac{C_{\text{IS}}}{A_{\text{IS}}} \times A_{\text{met}} \right) \quad (1)$$

2. For the lack of commercially available standards, the concentration of indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic acid, indole-3-propionic, methyl indole-3-acetate, *N*-acetyl tryptophan, tryptamine are determined with response factor (RF) Equation (2).

NOTE: use [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate as a C_{IS}

$$c_{\text{met}} = \left(\frac{C_{\text{IS}}}{A_{\text{IS}}} \times A_{\text{met}} \right) : \text{RF} \quad (2)$$

RF are calculated from Indolmix and Labelled standard mix determined in Equation (3)

$$\text{RF} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{met}}}{A_{\text{IS}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{IS}}}{C_{\text{met}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

NOTE: no normalization used

LC-QQQ method setup

Multisampler settings

Injection volume			2 µL
Needle Wash			Multi-wash
Stoptime			As Pump/No Limit
Posttime			Off
Advanced	Sampling Speed	Draw Speed	100 µL/min
		Eject Speed	100 µL/min
		Wait time After Draw	0 s
	Needle Height position	Offset	-0.4 mm
		Use Vial/Well Bottom Sensing	Yes
	High Throughput	Sample Flush-Out factor	5.0
		Injection Valve to Bypass for Delay Volume Reduction	No
		Enable Overlapped Injection	No

Binary Pump

Flow	0.3 mL/min		
Solvents	A:	0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water	
	B:	0.1% FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile	
Pressure limits	Min	0 bar	
	Max	1200 bar	
Stoptime	14 min		
Posttime	Off		
Advanced: Timetable	Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]
	0	95	5
	5	90	10
	10	5	95
	11.99	5	95
	12.00	95	5
	14.00	95	5

Column comp

Temperature	40 °C		
Advanced	Enable analysis	When temperature is within	± 0.8 °C

QQQ

Source parameters	Gas Temp:	160 °C
	Gas Flow:	15 L/min
	Nebulizer:	25 psi
	Sheath Gas Temp:	250 °C
	Sheath Gas Flow:	12 L/min

iFunnel parameters	Capillary:	3500 V (Positive)	3000 V (Negative)
	Nozzle Voltage:	500 V (Positive)	1500 V (Negative)
	High Pressure RF	150 V (Positive)	90 V (Negative)
	Low Pressure RF	60 V (Positive)	60 V (Negative)
Chromatogram	Stop Time		
	No limit/As Pump		
Time segments	Ion source	AJS ESI	
	Time filtering	Peak width	0.05 min
	Start Time	Scan type	Div Valve
	1	0	MRM
2	10.5	MRM	To Waste

Column & guard column: Acquity UHPLC CSHTM C18 column (100 x 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm) & VanGuard ACQUITY UPLC CSH C18 (5 x 2.1 mm; 1.7 µm) from Waters